

The Role of MSMEs in Increasing Visits in Cisoka Blue Lake, Tangerang Regency, Banten Province, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Cisoka Blue Lake, located in Tangerang Regency, is an attractive tourist destination. One factor contributing to increasing tourist attraction is the role of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). This research aims to explore the role of MSMEs in increasing tourist visits to Cisoka Blue Lake and the challenges faced by MSME actors in the tourism sector. A qualitative approach with descriptive methods was used in this research, which included in-depth interviews, direct observation and documentation. The research results show that local products such as souvenirs, traditional food, and handicrafts significantly improve the tourist experience and introduce local culture. Interaction between MSMEs and tourists also enjoy the tourism experience, creating mutually beneficial social relationships. However, several challenges, such as limited promotion and inadequate infrastructure, still hamper the development of MSMEs. Therefore, this research suggests increasing training for MSME players, improving infrastructure, and closer collaboration between tourism managers and MSMEs to increase tourist attraction and visits. Improving the quality and promotion of local products will positively impact the local economy and the welfare of the tourism sector.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cisoka Blue Lake is a natural tourist destination in Tangerang Regency, Banten Province. The natural beauty of Blue Lake, such as clear blue air and beautiful surrounding views, makes it a potential tourist destination in this region (Nurbaeti, 2022). However, to maximize this tourism potential, close collaboration is needed between various parties, including the important role of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector around the tourist area. MSMEs have a strategic role in creating an environment that supports the growth of the tourism sector, which will increase the number of tourist visits (Yansen et al., 2024).

The development of MSMEs in Indonesia has significantly contributed to the national economy, especially in creating jobs and driving the wheels of the local economy (Wahyudi et al., 2024). As a sector that can grow quickly and flexibly, MSMEs can provide products and services relevant to market needs, including in the tourism sector (Salsabila et al., 2024). MSMEs around Cisoka Blue Lake not only play a role as providers of local products but also enhance the tourist experience by providing typical culinary delights, souvenirs, and various tourist services.

The tourism sector, especially those that focus on natural tourism, needs more than just natural beauty to attract

the attention of tourists (Nurbaeti et al., 2021). Other supporting factors, such as visitor comfort, diversity of local products, and adequate services, also greatly influence tourists' decisions in choosing a destination (Mihai et al., 2023). MSMEs have great potential in providing these things, such as local products, which are an attraction for tourists who want to take home mementoes, as well as facilities that make travel easier, such as tour guide services, local transportation, and places to eat that serve culinary delight typical (Hermawan et al., 2024).

Apart from that, the role of MSMEs cannot be underestimated in the context of tourism promotion. The products produced by MSMEs often represent the local identity and culture around Blue Lake. In this way, MSMEs function as "cultural ambassadors" who introduce local uniqueness to tourists, while enhancing the image of Blue Lake as an authentic tourist destination that has its own charm. Various promotional efforts carried out by MSMEs, both through social media and collaboration with travel agents and tourism managers, can introduce Cisoka Blue Lake to a broader audience.

This research aims to analyze the extent of the role of MSMEs in increasing tourist visits to Cisoka Blue Lake, as well as understand what factors influence the effectiveness of

MSMEs in supporting the tourism sector. By knowing this, recommendations can be found that can increase synergy between the MSME and tourism sectors and positively impact local economic development. This research also aims to explore the further potential that MSMEs can utilize in the Blue Lake area to increase tourist attraction and the desire for tourism management in the region.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are integral to the Indonesian economy, significantly contributing to job creation and economic equality (Nugroho et al., 2024). According to Law No. 20 of 2008, MSMEs meet specific criteria based on total income or assets. In Indonesia, this sector has a strategic role in the national economy, significantly contributing to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and reducing poverty levels (Devita & Umaryadi, 2024). As flexible and innovative economic actors, MSMEs can survive various changing economic conditions, often becoming the main pillars of local economic development, including tourism (Irawati et al., 2024).

The tourism sector is an industry that is very dependent on the role of MSMEs. MSMEs in tourism include various business forms, such as culinary, souvenirs, lodging, tour guide services, and rental of tourist equipment (Subawa et al., 2022). MSMEs have a vital role in improving the quality of tourist experiences; the products and services produced by MSMEs provide added value that makes tourist destinations more attractive and allows tourists to experience a more authentic experience (Anugrahani et al., 2024). Therefore, the role of MSMEs in creating unique and immersive tourism experiences is vital in attracting visitor interest (Moisa et al., 2024).

Collaboration between MSMEs and the tourism sector is an effective strategy to increase the attractiveness of a tourist destination; partnerships between MSMEs and tourist attraction managers can create mutually beneficial synergies (Budilaksono et al., 2022). For MSMEs, the tourism sector provides a broader market and the potential for large profits, meanwhile, for the tourism sector, the presence of MSMEs provides added value, such as regional culinary specialties, souvenir products and services that can increase visitor satisfaction (Hermawan et al., 2024). In tourist destinations, this collaboration can also create a more comprehensive experience for tourists, enjoying natural beauty and interacting with local culture and products (Hidayat et al., 2023).

Natural tourist destinations are the main attractions, with stunning natural views, clear blue air, and an unspoiled atmosphere. However, natural beauty alone is not enough to attract tourists in large numbers (Kartika et al., 2024). Other factors, such as visitor comfort, ease of access, and supporting facilities, are also very important (Apriyanti et al.,

2024). The role of MSMEs is very significant because they provide products and services that satisfy tourist experiences, such as typical food souvenirs and tourist services, such as equipment rental for activities around the lake. MSMEs have great potential in increasing the number of tourist visits in an area (Gegung, 2023).

Local products offered by MSMEs, such as traditional culinary delights and regional souvenirs, are often reasons for tourists to visit specific tourist destinations; apart from that, activities organized by MSMEs, such as fairs, cultural festivals, or other local events, can also attract the attention of tourists (Sari & Kustanti, 2022). Tourism activities involving MSMEs in the form of the promotion of local products or cultural activities can strengthen tourist attraction, thereby increasing the number of visits; good collaboration between MSMEs and tourism managers is essential to create a more attractive and sustainable tourist destination (Achmad et al., 2023).

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach with descriptive methods to explore the role of MSMEs in increasing tourist visits to Cisoka Blue Lake, Tangerang Regency. A qualitative approach was chosen because it allows researchers to understand phenomena that occur in-depth, such as interactions between MSMEs and tourists and the impact of MSMEs on tourism experiences. This approach also allows researchers to gain a more holistic understanding of the dynamics of the tourism sector in Cisoka Blue Lake by considering the various social, cultural and economic aspects involved in MSME activities in the area.

Data collection was carried out using various methods, namely in-depth interviews, direct observation and documentation. Interviews were conducted with a number of key informants, consisting of MSME actors, tourist attraction managers, and tourists who visited Cisoka Blue Lake. This interview aims to obtain information regarding the role of MSMEs in supporting tourism, the obstacles they face, and their impact on the number of tourist visits. In addition, direct observations were carried out to observe MSME activities at the location, interactions between MSME actors and tourists, and how MSME products and services improve the tourist experience. Documentation techniques are used to collect secondary data, such as reports or information related to the management of Cisoka Blue and activities organized by MSMEs around tourist attractions.

After the data was collected, analysis was carried out by grouping the data based on themes that emerged from interviews and observations. The data obtained will be analyzed to identify factors that influence the success of MSMEs in increasing tourist visits, as well as reveal the positive impacts and challenges faced by MSMEs in the tourism sector. The results of this analysis will provide an idea of how big a role MSMEs play in tourism development

in Cisoka Blue Lake and how collaboration between MSMEs and tourism managers can increase the attractiveness of this destination.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Role of MSMEs in Supporting Tourism

The role of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Cisoka Blue Lake is vital in supporting the development of the local tourism sector. Most of the MSME players in this area actively play a role in providing various products that can improve the tourist experience. These products include regional souvenirs, which are souvenirs for visitors and reflect local culture and traditions. In addition, traditional food served in small stalls or taverns allows tourists to enjoy authentic regional flavours, often the main attraction for travellers. Typical regional handicrafts are also a popular choice, appealing to domestic and foreign tourists who want to take home unique memories from their travels.

Apart from products, supporting services provided by MSME players also play an equally important role in increasing tourist comfort and satisfaction. Comfortable resting areas and adequate parking facilities make it easy for visitors to enjoy the atmosphere without worrying about their physical comfort. Local tour guides are also very supportive because they direct tourists in exploring destinations and provide insight into history, culture and local values, making the visit even more meaningful. With all their contributions, MSMEs function as support for the local economy and as an important element in enriching a more authentic and memorable tourism experience for every visitor who comes.

The role of MSMEs is very significant in improving the tourist experience. The products offered by MSMEs provide added value to tourism activities and help maintain local cultural diversity. Interaction between MSME players and tourists is a means of introducing more profound local culture and traditions. Tourists who buy local products get souvenirs and learn more about the rich culture around Cisoka Blue Lake.

Interaction between MSMEs and Tourists

The interaction between MSMEs and tourists at Cisoka Blue Lake is well-established and mutually beneficial. Based on direct monitoring, many tourists visit the MSME kiosks scattered around this tourist destination. MSME players not only offer their products, but also actively interact with tourists, provide information about the products being sold, and explain the history and uniqueness of Blue Lake. Vendors often share stories about the origins of their wares, be they handicrafts, speciality foods, or souvenirs, which add value to the tourist experience. This kind of interaction encourages economic transactions and creates social relationships that strengthen ties between visitors and local communities.

More than just a place to shop, this MSME kiosk allows tourists to learn about local culture firsthand. By getting

information about local traditions, customs and stories told by MSME actors, tourists get a more in-depth and authentic experience. This enriches their knowledge about the uniqueness of the places they visit so that their trip is not just for tourism but also to understand and appreciate the rich culture around them. This interaction creates a pleasant atmosphere; both tourists and MSMEs share knowledge while increasing the attractiveness of Blue Lake as a tourist destination that offers natural beauty and a strong and unique culture.

The research results revealed that MSMEs play an important role in increasing the attractiveness of tourist destinations. The products and services offered by MSMEs not only support tourist comfort but also function as one factor influencing tourists' decisions to visit Blue Lake. This increase in tourist visits certainly positively impacts the local community's economy, considering that many tourists spend their money buying local products, which ultimately benefits MSMEs.

The impact of MSMEs on the number of tourist visits

The impact of MSMEs on the number of tourist visits to Cisoka Blue Lake can be seen through a significant increase in the number of visitors, especially on weekends and holidays. Based on data obtained from tourist attraction managers, a number of tourists came to this destination during these periods. This shows that MSMEs are very important in attracting tourists to visit more often. The existence of MSMEs that offer typical products, such as souvenirs, traditional food and handicrafts, has provided an additional attraction for visitors who want to take home memories from their travels. These products are why many tourists spend more time at Blue Lake, exploring each stall and looking for unique items that can only be found there.

Apart from that, the role of MSMEs in increasing the length of tourist visits is very significant. With various attractive product choices, tourists come to enjoy the view and shop and chat with MSME players. Some tourists even spend more time around tourist locations because they are attracted by the wide selection of goods for sale and want to take advantage of the opportunity to buy quality souvenirs. This undoubtedly contributes to improving the local economy because the longer tourists stay in the area, the greater the potential for their shopping. Overall, MSMEs help increase the number of visits and extend the duration of visits, thereby positively impacting tourism desires in Blue Lake.

Even though the contribution of MSMEs to tourism is very large, several challenges faced by MSMEs need to be considered. One is limited infrastructure, affecting tourist comforts, such as damaged roads and minimal sanitation facilities. Therefore, an active role is needed from tourist attraction managers and local governments to improve the infrastructure around Blue Lake, so that it can create a more supportive environment for MSME activities.

Challenges faced by MSMEs

MSMEs around Cisoka Blue Lake face challenges that hinder their development and competitiveness in supporting the tourism industry. One of the main challenges is limiting effective promotions. Many MSME players have difficulty reaching broader markets, both at the local and national levels. Limited promotion means the products they offer are not widely known, even though these products have the potential to attract the attention of tourists. Without an appropriate marketing strategy, MSMEs have difficulty introducing their products outside the scope of tourists who already come to the location. Limited access to larger markets is also a significant obstacle because many MSME players do not have a wide enough distribution network to sell their products outside the Blue Lake area.

Apart from promotional problems, inadequate infrastructure is also a big challenge for MSMEs in this area. Damaged roads and lack of adequate sanitation facilities reduce tourist comfort, which in turn can decrease visits. Poor infrastructure makes accessibility to Blue Lake more difficult for tourists and business people. Furthermore, several MSME players also complained about the lack of training that focuses on professional business management. Many MSMEs have difficulty managing their business well, optimizing product potential, and maintaining service quality without adequate training. As a result, the potential of MSMEs cannot be fully exploited, and they have difficulty competing with other, more professional businesses and are ready to face more considerable market challenges.

Collaboration between MSMEs and tourism managers is still limited and needs to be improved. Closer cooperation, such as holding events or joint promotions, could help introduce Cisoka Blue Lake more widely. Tourism managers can act as facilitators in supporting MSMEs, for example, by providing space for MSMEs to promote or provide training on marketing and more professional business management.

Collaboration between MSMEs and Tourism Managers

Collaboration between MSMEs and tourist attraction managers at Cisoka Blue Lake is still limited, even though the potential for synergy between the two is vast to support the progress of the local tourism sector. Several MSME players expressed their hope for closer cooperation with tourist attraction managers, such as holding joint events that could attract more visitors or more intense joint promotions. Collaboration like this can widely introduce MSME products to tourists while providing a richer tourism experience. However, so far, the form of collaboration that has been established is still not optimal, and several MSMEs feel that they do not receive optimal support from tourism managers to develop their businesses simultaneously.

However, several positive initiatives have been carried out, such as providing a place for MSMEs to open kiosks in the Blue Lake tourist area. This initiative provides an

opportunity for MSMEs to increase exposure of their products to tourists who come to the location. With kiosks located at strategic points, local speciality products can be more easily reached by visitors, and this also has the potential to increase the attraction of tourists to stay longer at Blue Lake. However, MSME actors hope this collaboration can be further strengthened with support from tourism managers in joint promotions, training, or organizing activities that involve both parties more intensively. More solid cooperation will help improve the quality of tourism services while positively impacting the local economy.

To increase the role of MSMEs in the tourism sector, it is necessary to increase training and assistance for MSME players. This can include training in business management, digital marketing, and better financial management. Apart from that, tourist attraction managers must also provide further support in joint promotions and improve infrastructure and facilities to create a better tourist experience for visitors.

V. CONCLUSION

MSMEs play a strategic role in supporting the development of the tourism sector in Cisoka Blue Lake, Tangerang Regency. Local products produced by MSMEs, such as traditional food, regional souvenirs and handicrafts, provide significant added value to the tourist experience. Apart from that, the services provided by MSMEs, such as comfortable resting places, parking facilities, and competent local tour guides, also contribute to creating comfort for visitors. Interaction between MSME players and tourists in the Blue Lake area increases economic transactions and introduces more profound local culture and traditions. Tourists who buy local products get mementoes and learn about the rich culture around them, making the travel experience more authentic and meaningful. The presence of MSMEs around this tourist attraction also enriches the destination by offering things that are not only interesting in terms of natural scenery but also in terms of the richness of local culture and traditions that live in the daily activities of local people.

However, even though the role of MSMEs in the tourism sector in Cisoka Blue Lake is vital, several challenges MSME players face need serious attention. One of the main challenges is restrictions in terms of effective promotion and marketing. Many MSME players have difficulty reaching a broader local and national market, so their products are unknown. In addition, inadequate infrastructure, such as damaged roads and minimal sanitation facilities, reduces tourist comfort, affecting the number of visits. For this reason, closer cooperation is needed between tourist attraction managers and MSMEs to improve infrastructure, increase joint promotions, and train MSME actors. Improving digital marketing and business management skills will help MSMEs compete more

effectively to maximize the potential of their products and make a more significant contribution to the local economy. A more solid collaboration between MSMEs and tourism managers can create mutually beneficial synergies, enrich the tourist experience, and increase the attractiveness of Cisoka Blue Lake as a sustainable and attractive tourist destination for visitors.

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